

PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This interim deliverable (D7.3) presents an overview of the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities carried out by the PRO-CLIMATE consortium during the first 18 months of the project. It assesses the implementation of the strategy outlined in the initial D7.1 plan and provides early insights into the visibility, outreach, and stakeholder engagement achieved so far. The report captures key achievements across various channels—including the project website, social media platforms, newsletters, press releases, publications, and event participation—while also describing the processes used for monitoring and reporting D&C efforts internally among partners.

The deliverable highlights the successful establishment of the project's visual identity, the growing digital presence, and the strategic use of media and events to raise awareness about the project's goals and activities. Furthermore, it documents the establishment of valuable synergies with sister and other related EU-funded projects. These collaborations have already resulted in joint sessions, shared knowledge products, and co-branded events that amplify PRO-CLIMATE's impact. The report concludes with a forward-looking perspective, outlining upcoming dissemination activities and emphasizing the importance of adaptive planning and cross-project cooperation to ensure the lasting relevance and uptake of PRO-CLIMATE's outcomes.

1 Introduction

1.1 The PRO-CLIMATE Project

The PRO-CLIMATE (Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change) project aims to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE will adopt an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems that are interconnected and influenced by multiple factors, socio-economic and environmental. By understanding and leveraging their dynamics, it will then develop strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This will result in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to foster proactively adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes. A set of diverse (in terms of climate change problems and socio-economic contexts) case studies across Europe will be an instrumental tool for the co-creation, validation, and upscaling of this framework by running living labs and bringing stakeholders together to understand community governance and institutional structures, and to also pilot and validate the project's behavioural change activities. The outputs of PRO-CLIMATE include:

- a. the identification of key components of climate adaptation systems, their interactions, systemic interdependencies and trade-offs,
- b. the design, implementation, and evaluation of a living lab framework,
- c. the identification of social tipping points and leverage actions for policy makers,
- d. the development of a multi agent computer model for European socio-ecological systems to allow a realistic analysis of existing and future policy scenarios likely to produce systemic transformations, and
- e. policy recommendations to accelerate systemic change.

1.2 Description of WP7

WP7 incorporates PRO-CLIMATE activities related to publicity/awareness of the project, dissemination of results and relevant communication with external stakeholders/interested parties. These publicity and dissemination activities have been designed to reflect the project's needs and characteristics and are closely related to the post-project continuation and sustainability plans. It also collects lessons learned and obtains feedback from a broader network of projects through clustering with other EU projects. The specific tasks of WP7 are the following:

- Task 7.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.2: Dissemination activities (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.3: Communication activities (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.4: Cooperation and clustering with other projects (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.5: Exploitation prospects (M4 – M36)

1.3 Purpose and Scope

This document presents the mid-term review of dissemination and communication (D&C) efforts conducted during the first 18 months of the PRO-CLIMATE project. It aims to assess the implementation of the D&C strategy outlined in Deliverable D7.1, evaluating the reach, engagement, and visibility generated through the planned activities. The document serves to inform the consortium, stakeholders, and the European Commission about the progress made in building awareness, fostering stakeholder interaction, and supporting the uptake of project outcomes.

The deliverable also acts as a reference point for evaluating the effectiveness and relevance of tools and channels used so far. It enables the consortium to reflect on what worked well, identify areas for improvement, and refine its approach for the remaining implementation period. By doing so, it contributes to maximizing the project's impact and sustaining its results beyond the funding duration.

1.4 Structure of the document

The document discusses and analyses the Dissemination and Communication activities which have been implemented within the project from each very beginning until M18 out of a total 36 months project duration. D7.3 “Dissemination and Communication Impact Report Interim version involves numerous sections:

- a. **Section 1 – Introduction:**
Provides an overview of the PRO-CLIMATE project, introduces the objectives and scope of Work Package 7 (WP7), and explains the purpose of this deliverable. It also outlines the structure of the document and its connection to related deliverables.
- b. **Section 2 – Periodic Report:** Details the methodology and tools used to monitor dissemination and communication activities. It presents the outcomes of all D&C efforts including branding materials, the project website, social media engagement, press releases, newsletters, and scientific publications.
- c. **Section 3 – Organisation of Workshops and Networking Events:** Summarises the key dissemination events, stakeholder workshops, and outreach sessions organized by the consortium to foster engagement and visibility.
- d. **Section 4 – Clustering and Joint Activities with Other Projects and Initiatives:** Highlights synergies and collaborative actions undertaken with other EU-funded projects, including co-hosted events, thematic exchanges, interviews, and future opportunities for alignment.
- e. **Appendices:**
Includes supporting material, templates, and documentation referenced throughout the report, such as visual identity elements and additional resources.

1.5 Relationship with other deliverables

The broader goal of the dissemination and communication strategy of PRO-CLIMATE is to raise awareness in diverse environments and ensure that the results are leveraged by the identified stakeholder groups. Hence, the overall project Dissemination and Communication Plan is directly associated with the outcomes of the different WPs in the project since they feed useful content to be disseminated from the partnership. As all WP7 actions are interlinked, the current deliverable D7.3 is related with the other WP7 activities and deliverables and the table below describes the dependencies and relations.

Table 1: Relationships with other PRO-CLIMATE deliverables

WP7 Deliverables	Dependencies and Relation
D7.1 Publicity and Dissemination Plan Draft version	D7.1 outlines the initial strategy for the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities of the PRO-CLIMATE project, as developed and agreed upon by the consortium during the early stages of implementation. Delivered at Month 6 (M6), this draft plan serves as a foundational document to guide outreach efforts, stakeholder engagement, and visibility actions. It establishes the key messages, target audiences, and communication channels to be used throughout the project. The plan is designed to be a living document, reviewed and refined over time based on emerging needs and feedback, leading up to the updated and final version in D7.2 at Month 24 (M24).
D7.2 Publicity and Dissemination Plan Final	D7.2 is an updated version of the current document that will be delivered on M24 of the project. During these 18 months from the delivery of D7.1 on M6 to the delivery of the updated

	<p>version in D7.2, the Dissemination and Communication plan will be monitored and updated on a regular basis with the objective to make sure that the appropriate target messages and being reached to the appropriate audience and the project is maximizing its impact.</p>
D7.4 Dissemination & Communication Impact Report Final version	<p>D7.4 will provide a report about the overall progress of WP7 from M19 to M36, with emphasis on the dissemination and communication activities performed during this period, the benefits of the various stakeholders involved, the synergies developed with existing initiatives, the roadmap for expansion and the guide for replication of research and services.</p>

2. Periodic Report

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Reporting Process

2.1.1 Purpose of the reporting process

This section describes the process followed by the PRO-CLIMATE partners in order to report their dissemination and communication activities. Dissemination activities are essential for the impact maximisation, visibility and exploitation of the progress and findings of PRO-CLIMATE across the project target groups and audiences. What is more, dissemination and communication of the project results are contractual obligations stated in the project's Grant Agreement. For this reason, all PRO-CLIMATE partners make sure to engage in dissemination and communication activities and keep track of all these activities and their outreach and performance.

2.1.2 About the PRO-CLIMATE Dissemination and Communication Activities Reporting Tool

The PRO-CLIMATE Dissemination and Communication Activities Reporting is an online tool used by all the consortium partners to report and keep track of the dissemination and communication activities that have been implemented throughout the project. The dissemination and communication reporting tool is available online and can be accessed internally by the consortium members through their private Shared Drive. All the PRO-CLIMATE consortium partners have to report any dissemination and communication activity they implement to the online reporting tool. The types of such activities that PRO-CLIMATE partners could potentially engage with are:

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to an Event, other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities, organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Liaison Synergies)
- Training Session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Videos
- Other

The dissemination and communication reporting is an internal process among the consortium partners, employed to feed the project website with information about the reported activities, share the reported information through the PRO-CLIMATE social media and analyse the information to extract statistics and conclusions about the progress and performance of the project's dissemination and communication strategy.

2.2 Project Branding

This section of the document reports all the dissemination and communication activities that were implemented within PRO-CLIMATE from M1 until M18 of the project.

2.2.1 Visual Identity

From M1 until M3 of the project, communication efforts focused on building the branding and visual identity of the PRO-CLIMATE Project. To this end, several communication artefacts, materials, templates as well as a project logo were developed.

2.2.1.1 Logo

The PRO-CLIMATE project logo (Figure 1) ensures the recognition of the project among all target audiences and it is used in all the dissemination materials, documents, presentations, etc. in a prominent way. This logo has been developed in various resolutions, formats and versions (text incl.).

Figure 1: PRO-CLIMATE Logo

2.2.1.2 Document and presentation templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates were developed in the beginning of the project to maintain coherence among the many different documents produced. Those templates include a deliverable and document template, as well as a presentation template, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 4: PRO-CLIMATE banner 2nd version

Figure 5: PRO-CLIMATE roll-up banner in two version

2.2.1.4 Project presentation

An overall project presentation of PRO-CLIMATE was created and uploaded in the project’s SlideShare channel¹. The PRO-CLIMATE project presentation includes all the important information that create a clear understanding of the project’s concept, challenges, expected impact and outputs as well as foreseen activities (Figure 6). The presentation has been viewed by over 150 users.

Figure 6: PRO-CLIMATE general presentation

2.2.1.5 Project Card

In the context of the PRO-CLIMATE project, we have also developed two versions of the project’s card for communication and dissemination purposes. These are included in Figure 7 and 8 below:

Figure 7: PRO-CLIMATE Project Card Version 1

¹ <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/proactive-community-adaptation-to-climate-change-through-social-transformation-and-behavioural-change/272236077>

Figure 8: PRO-CLIMATE Project Card Version 2

2.2.1.6 Certificate

The PRO-CLIMATE Certificate of Attendance is designed as a formal acknowledgment for participants who attend project-related workshops, meetings, or training events.

Figure 9: PRO-CLIMATE Certificate of Attendance

2.2.1.7 PRO-CLIMATE thank you letter to stakeholders

To acknowledge and reinforce the valuable contributions of stakeholders involved in PRO-CLIMATE activities, the consortium has developed a dedicated thank you letter. This letter is shared following participation in key events and workshops, serving both as a gesture of appreciation and as a means of strengthening ongoing relationships. It highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement in achieving the project’s objectives and encourages continued collaboration throughout the journey toward climate resilience. The letter also helps foster trust, visibility, and a sense of shared ownership among all involved. The letter is presented below.

Figure 10: Thank you letter

2.2.2 Video

Within the PRO-CLIMATE project, we have developed a general project video which showcases in an interesting and visual way the project’s objectives, methodological approach, expected outcomes and communication channels. The video is available to the project's YouTube channel here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uDKbHI_Q3T4 subtitled in all languages that PRO-CLIMATE LLs are hosted.

Figure 11: Project video screenshot

2.3 The PRO-CLIMATE Project Website

2.3.1 About the website

One of the most crucial tools for the successful dissemination and communication of the results of PRO-CLIMATE is the project’s website, whose first version launched on the first month (M1) of its lifecycle (January 2024). The current version of the PRO-CLIMATE’s website homepage is available in Figure 12. The website domain name is <https://pro-climate.eu/>. All the necessary information regarding the structure and progress of the project as well as the project’s news, materials, etc. are uploaded on the website. In particular, the PRO-CLIMATE website aims to:

- Provide information about the project, its main objectives, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which PRO-CLIMATE members participate, information about the consortium, an option to subscribe to the project’s newsletter, social media channels and further contact information.
- Communicate the actual value stemming from the project to all target groups and audiences in order to encourage their participation in the project’s activities. Due to the fact that the website is the project’s main portal for communicating its outputs and results with its target audiences, it is constantly updated with new content and adjusted according to the project’s advancements and results.

Figure 12: Website screenshot

2.3.2 Structure of the Website and main sections

As previously mentioned, as the project progresses, new content is constantly uploaded on the PRO-CLIMATE website, to keep visitors up to date with the project advances. The current structure of the PRO-CLIMATE website homepage is presented below. The main sections of the website are:

- The project’s description: This includes the approach, objectives, expected results, consortium members, etc.
- Resources: This includes all dissemination and communication material produced and available for public use.
- Living Labs: Information for our six (6) living labs, their description and activities up until now.

- News & Events: In this section all the news and relevant events of PRO-CLIMATE are accessible by the public.

2.3.3 News items

As mentioned above, the PRO-CLIMATE website currently has a number of 21 news items as well as 1 newsletter and 3 press releases. The news items are published in the “News” section of the website, including the latest news and updates stemming from the project.

2.3.4 Performance and outreach

The PRO-CLIMATE website significantly contributes to the dissemination of key messages produced in the project, reaching a broad audience of stakeholders daily. From M1 until M18, the project website had more than 1.300 users who on average engaged with website’s content for 1min duration. Website traffic is also presented in Figure 13 through Google Analytics.

As PRO-CLIMATE’s main communication tool, the project website will continue to be frequently updated, so that new content reaches the target audiences. The consortium partners play a key role in this process, since they constantly contribute material from all related activities to be used.

Figure 13: Website statistics

2.4 Social media

2.4.1 PRO-CLIMATE Social Media channels

PRO-CLIMATE’s social media channels are a much-needed part of its dissemination and communication strategy, since they allow engaging stakeholders with the project’s activities and news, while creating a space where interaction is enabled, as well as discussions and provision of feedback. Through the use of social media, PRO-CLIMATE manages to build a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences and sustain a well-informed group of target audiences, which enhances project’s overall impact.

Through LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Bluesky and YouTube, information about the project’s status and activities are made available to the public. The links of the PRO-CLIMATE social media channels are the following:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/pro-climate-project/>
- X: https://x.com/PRO_CLIMATE_EU

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/proclimate.project>
- Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/pro-climate.bsky.social>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@PRO-CLIMATE.project>

The use of appropriate social media channels to communicate and disseminate messages regarding the project can significantly help PRO-CLIMATE increase its reach to the appropriate target audiences. In the sections below, the outreach achieved through the social media accounts of the PRO-CLIMATE project will be reviewed.

2.4.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is an online Social Media Platform that allows for targeted outreach to the specified target audiences with specific professional interests. Through LinkedIn, PRO-CLIMATE managed to reach approximately 13k user views until M18 of the project. Currently, PRO-CLIMATE has 532 followers on LinkedIn and 39 posts in total.

2.4.3 X

X (formerly Twitter) is a micro-blogging social media platform and stands among the most popular ones available on the internet. X's audience is plugged-in, receptive, and dynamic, which enables the broadcast of messages to a captive audience more easily. Until M18, PRO-CLIMATE achieved approximately a significant number of impressions while currently, PRO-CLIMATE has 94 followers on Twitter and 34 posts.

2.4.4 Facebook

Facebook is an online social media platform with billions of monthly active users, providing a very broad audience to reach out to. To this extent PRO-CLIMATE managed to reach more than 1.1k user views until M18 of the project while having a total number of 39 followers.

2.4.5 Bluesky

Bluesky is a social media platform and has a growing audience. Currently, PRO-CLIMATE has 16 followers on Bluesky and 11 posts in total while the account was created in Month 6 of the project's implementation.

2.4.6 YouTube

Video content production can be a powerful tool to spread a message in a pertinent and easy to understand manner to a wider audience. For this reason, PRO-CLIMATE has produced one general project video and uploaded it on its YouTube channel and other social media pages. Currently, 1 video has been uploaded on the PRO-CLIMATE YouTube Channel, counting more than 130 views in total.

2.4.7 Posts on partners' social media

Additionally, all project partners in PRO-CLIMATE use their own social media platforms to post about the results and activities of the project, acting as essential multipliers for the outreach of the project. Multipliers are social media channels that could potentially facilitate the direct engagement with more users and thus, enable the dissemination of content such as articles, photos and videos to a broader audience, while simultaneously assisting the creation of brand affinity. This process significantly facilitates the growth of the PRO-CLIMATE community and fosters stakeholder engagement.

2.5 Press Releases

In the first 18 months of the project, several Press Releases have been produced about the news of the PRO-CLIMATE Project, both in English as well as in local partner languages, and disseminated through different platforms and media. The official Press Releases produced until M18 by the project is:

- a. PRO-CLIMATE Horizon Europe project kicked off: https://pro-climate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/PRO-CLIMATE_Press_Release_20240105.pdf
- b. How Europe's communities are taking climate resilience into their hands: https://pro-climate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/PRO-CLIMATE_Press_Release_20241015.pdf
- c. Living Lab Workshop in Zakynthos Tackles Sustainable Tourism and Climate Resilience: https://pro-climate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/PRO-CLIMATE_Press_Release_20250321.pdf

These are complemented by press releases published and disseminated by the consortium members in their local languages and which are included in the D&C reporting table in Annex 1.

2.6 PRO-CLIMATE Newsletters

2.6.1 PRO-CLIMATE Newsletter n.1

The first PRO-CLIMATE newsletter circulated on M13 (February 2025) of the project, with the aim to formally update the target groups for the project's update and overall progress and to inform the community about its news and advances. PRO-CLIMATE's first newsletter reached more than 150 recipients. The full newsletter can be accessed through the link below:

Newsletter link: <https://mailchi.mp/722c63be83a4/pro-climate-newsletter>.

[View this email in your browser](#)

Empowering Communities for a Resilient Future

The PRO-CLIMATE project is driving **climate adaptation** by fostering **social transformation** and **behavioral change**. Through six Living Labs across Europe, it is generating valuable insights into community-led resilience.

Launched in January 2024, PRO-CLIMATE is funded by the European Commission under the HORIZON-CL5-2023-D1-01-09 topic:

Figure 14: PRO-CLIMATE 1st newsletter

2.6.2 PRO-CLIMATE Featured in MAIA Newsletter

Other than the newsletters produced within the framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project, the consortium partners have also included news and about PRO-CLIMATE on other newsletters such as MAIA's EU project and various European networks.

2.7 Publications

PRO-CLIMATE partners are devoted to the creation of scientific articles, published in the international scientific literature, when possible. All partners acknowledge their common interest in publishing the knowledge to obtain recognition and to advance the state of knowledge in the field. All scientific publications published within the framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project are available below:

Air and Water Components of the environment

Title: Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change' – Gdansk case study

The 3 year project (2024-2026), PRO-CLIMATE (Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change), outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 6 Living Labs (LLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance climate resilience and achieve systemic transformations through behavioural change and good governance. The escalating of extreme weather events, sea-level rise and coastal erosion have an increasingly significant impact on the lives of residents of European cities. LLs are situated in Sligo (Ireland), Leipzig (Germany), Badajoz (Spain), Bergen (Norway), Zakynthos (Greece) and Gdansk (Poland). For Gdansk LL the most important risk is urban flash flooding caused due to increasingly frequent torrential rain. A detailed analysis of flood events and its effects from 2001 to 2017 is the base for fostering significant and sustainable change within the LL community. 8-Step Process for Leading Change conducted by the core LL team and the 'ideal' change agent) (built on Kotter's model), plays a crucial role in driving and supporting the change process. All case studies will be utilized to pilot and validate the project's behavioural change activities.

3rd International Conference 'Lakes & Reservoirs: Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology'

Title: Methods for engaging local communities in adaptation activities

Abstract: Multicriteria Analysis as a method for engaging stakeholders and citizens in activities aimed at supporting climate resilience and adaptation to climate change –Gdansk Living Lab

2nd Geogame Symposium in Dublin

Title: The use of serious games in Living Labs

Abstract: Living lab has emerged in recent years as intermediaries for open innovations, solving social challenges, and enhancing knowledge sharing through participatory approaches. How to motivate stakeholders' participation and keep active engagement are always the central question to succeed in a living lab. Serious games have been proved through research that they can help to improve stakeholder engagement in traditionally non-gaming sectors, i.e. product design, marketing, social innovation. However, there is no study summarizing the use of serious games in living labs. Thus, this study aims to understand the current use of serious games in living labs. A systematic review is conducted for this study. The results show that most of the studies centred in the global north countries, especially the western European countries. The significant increase of the use of serious games in living labs starts in 2020. Geogames, Simulation games, Behavior games, Social-serious games, and Exergames are commonly used in different phases of living labs, submitted by Atlantic Technological University

SSC 2025 – Social Simulation Conference 2025

Title: Towards an ABM on Proactive Community Adaptation for Climate Change

Abstract: We present an agent-based model (ABM) simulating proactive community adaptation to climate change in an urban context. The model is applied to Bergen, Norway, represented as a complex socio-ecological system. It integrates multiple agent types: municipal government (urban planners and political actors), civil society (individual citizens), environmental NGOs and activists, and media. Agents interact during urban planning processes—particularly the evaluation and approval of new development proposals. Urban planners provide technical assessments, while politicians (organized by party) make final decisions to approve, modify, or reject projects. Environmental NGOs, activist groups, and the media shape public perception and influence policymakers through campaigns, lobbying, protests, and news coverage. Individual citizens decide whether to engage in collective action based on personal values and social influences. The model captures the resulting decision-making ecosystem and reveals feedback loops and leverage points that determine climate-adaptive outcomes. By analyzing these dynamics, we identify critical intervention points where targeted policy measures can facilitate systemic transformation toward more climate-resilient urban development.

Open Living Lab Days 2025

Title: Systemic Transformation for Climate Resilience: Insights from the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs submitted by Tero PC

PRO-CLIMATE article in GreenAgenda.gr: <https://greenagenda.gr/pro-climate-%b4%b7%bc%b9%bf%cf%85%cf%81%b3%af%b1-%bc%bf%bd%cf%84%ad%bb%bf%cf%85-%b3%b9%b1-%cf%84%b7-%cf%87%ac%cf%81%b1%be%b7-%cf%80/>

Figure 15: PRO-CLIMATE Article in Greenagenda.gr

3. Organisation of Workshops

3.1 Change Agents workshops

As part of PRO-CLIMATE's commitment to empowering local stakeholders and fostering behavioural change, two dedicated Change Agents Workshops have been held to support and strengthen the work of the project's six Living Labs. The first workshop, conducted in November 2024 in Coventry, served as a foundational meeting to introduce the Change Agents from across the consortium, establish a shared understanding of the behavioural change process, and begin mapping out stakeholder engagement strategies. This session marked the beginning of a structured and participatory journey to guide each Living Lab in developing context-specific approaches for climate adaptation, rooted in behavioural and governance transformation.

Figure 16: 1st Change Agent workshop in Coventry, UK

The second workshop, held virtually on 31 March 2025, continued this collaborative process by bringing together representatives from Work Package 4 (WP4), Change Agents from all Living Labs, and the Project Coordinator. The session, facilitated by Prof. Dr. Ann-Marie Nienaber and Dr. Kindy Sandhu, focused on assessing each Living Lab's progress in its change process, identifying key challenges in stakeholder engagement, and introducing tailored tools such as Memorandums of Understanding, certificates of participation, and communication strategies to reinforce community involvement. The workshop fostered cross-site learning and exchange, with participants sharing experiences and best practices in a spirit of collaboration. This peer-to-peer support not only enhanced the individual capacity of the Change Agents but also reinforced the project's overall coherence in fostering systemic, inclusive, and durable climate resilience across diverse European contexts.

3.2 Living Lab workshops

As part of Work Package 2 (WP2), the PRO-CLIMATE consortium has actively supported the establishment and operationalization of six Living Labs (LLs) across Europe, with a focus on stakeholder co-creation, participatory planning, and climate adaptation tailored to local socio-ecological realities. Numerous local workshops have been organized—both by project partners and independently by the Living Labs themselves—to initiate inclusive dialogue, identify focal action situations, and collaboratively define climate resilience priorities. These workshops have served as essential platforms for community engagement, trust-building, and the early co-design of adaptation strategies.

In Sligo, Ireland, a workshop brought together key local actors to explore ecosystem-based adaptation solutions to coastal erosion and flooding, emphasizing the integration of smart technologies and cross-sectoral collaboration. In Zakynthos, Greece, the inaugural workshop focused on the island's tourism-dependent economy, addressing climate impacts such as rising temperatures, fire risk, and coastal degradation. The session aimed to align sustainable tourism with climate resilience through stakeholder dialogue. Likewise, in Mérida, Spain, the first physical workshop launched the Badajoz Living Lab by convening regional stakeholders to address extreme heat, water scarcity, and the socio-demographic vulnerabilities of the area, setting a roadmap for future engagement.

The Leipzig and Gdańsk Living Labs are currently in earlier stages of development, with foundational workshops already held to catalyze discussion and define thematic focus. In Leipzig, stakeholders were engaged in developing a structured climate resilience strategy in response to updated municipal strategic priorities, with a specific focus on transitioning to heat pump technologies. The Leipzig Living Lab initially progressed slowly due to administrative coordination needs, but has since accelerated significantly. The city recognizes the Lab as a valuable process and actively engages with it while revising its climate adaptation strategy, which is to be completed by the end of 2025.

In Gdańsk, the workshop served to map stakeholder expectations and explore the potential of nature-based solutions (NBS) for flood mitigation, especially in light of intensifying rainfall and storm events. These early steps are critical in laying the groundwork for community ownership and systemic change within each local context.

In Zakynthos, the process was further advanced through two additional workshops held in February and April 2025, organized in partnership with Co-opAbility. These sessions deepened the initial stakeholder engagement by facilitating structured dialogue among local authorities, tourism operators, environmental groups, and residents. The February workshop focused on participatory mapping of climate risks and resource challenges, while the April session emphasized collaborative development of adaptation pathways that balance environmental protection with economic viability. Key themes included seasonal tourism pressures, water resource conservation, and fire prevention measures.

The repeated engagement in Zakynthos reflects PRO-CLIMATE's commitment to iterative and inclusive co-creation. These workshops have not only helped to identify emerging priorities and actionable solutions but have also strengthened stakeholder relationships and reinforced the shared vision of climate-resilient transformation. Across all sites, the Living Lab workshops organized under WP2 serve as vital mechanisms for translating the project's theoretical frameworks into grounded, participatory actions—demonstrating how behavioral and systemic change can be mobilized at the local level for long-term impact.

4. Clustering and Joint Activities with other Projects and Initiatives

The PRO-CLIMATE project places strong emphasis on collaboration and knowledge exchange with other EU-funded initiatives working in the fields of climate resilience, behavioral change, and systemic transformation. Clustering activities are a key element of the project's dissemination and impact strategy, as they enable mutual learning, resource sharing, and the amplification of results through collective action. This section outlines the various synergies developed to date, including formal and informal partnerships, co-organized events, cross-promotion of tools and methodologies, and upcoming joint initiatives. These collaborative efforts contribute not only to the visibility of PRO-CLIMATE but also to the broader European agenda for integrated and citizen-centered climate adaptation.

4.1 NEURO-CLIMA KoM

As part of its early clustering and networking activities, PRO-CLIMATE participated in the kick-off meeting of the NEUROCLIMA project, which took place in January 2024. This initial engagement provided an opportunity to establish a mutual understanding between the two sister projects, explore thematic overlaps, and lay the groundwork for future collaboration. The meeting included presentations of project objectives, discussion on potential synergies—particularly in the areas of behavioral change and systemic resilience—and an open exchange of ideas on how to align dissemination efforts. This marked the beginning of a constructive relationship that continues to evolve through joint actions and shared events.

Link: <https://pro-climate.eu/pro-climate-the-kick-off-meeting-of-neuroclima/>

Figure 17: PRO-CLIMATE's presentation in NEUROCLIMA KoM

4.2 Clustering activities

a. NEUROCLIMA

PRO-CLIMATE maintains an active and growing synergy with its sister project, NEUROCLIMA, aimed at strengthening collaboration on behavioral and systemic approaches to climate adaptation. The two consortia are exploring several concrete actions, including the potential signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) to formalize their partnership—especially in cases where the exchange of confidential material or coordinated research outputs would warrant it. Among the planned joint initiatives is an online webinar, tentatively scheduled for October–November 2025, with a working title such as *“Adaptation in Action: Behavioral and Systemic Pathways for a Resilient Europe”*. Both projects also expressed interest in co-authoring policy briefs and other targeted publications based on their collective insights, with a focus on influencing key stakeholders and decision-makers. Coordination around joint meetings is also under discussion, with the possibility of

NEUROCLIMA representatives joining the PRO-CLIMATE General Assembly in Gdansk (September 2025), as well as a potential follow-up meeting in Greece or Norway in early 2026. Finally, the two projects share enthusiasm for co-organizing a final joint event in Brussels in September 2026, which would serve as a high-level platform to disseminate shared results, showcase impact, and demonstrate alignment with broader EU climate adaptation initiatives, including those under MIP4Adaptation.

b. P2R

PRO-CLIMATE has also established a collaboration with the **Pathways2Resilience (P2R)** project, with the goal of enhancing synergies in the fields of community engagement, governance innovation, and climate resilience planning. An initial coordination meeting between the two consortia facilitated a rich exchange on key themes such as behavioral change, Living Lab methodologies, and the adaptation investment cycle. The collaboration envisions shared participation in deep dive sessions, exchange of guidance materials, joint events, and alignment of case study approaches. As highlighted in a recent article on the PRO-CLIMATE website, both projects recognize strong complementarities and are committed to fostering continued dialogue and cooperation to amplify the impact and relevance of their respective outcomes.

Link: <https://pro-climate.eu/pro-climate-and-pathways2resilience-collaboration/>

c. Regions4Climate

PRO-CLIMATE has also initiated a promising collaboration with the **Regions4Climate** project, aiming to strengthen mutual learning and exchange on regional climate adaptation and social resilience. As outlined in a recent news item on the PRO-CLIMATE website, the two projects held a dedicated online meeting to explore areas of complementarity and coordination. Discussions focused on behavioral change, stakeholder engagement, and the use of Living Labs as key tools for transformative adaptation. Both projects acknowledged the value of aligning their approaches and sharing insights, tools, and good practices. Building on this initial exchange, PRO-CLIMATE and Regions4Climate are actively seeking further opportunities for joint activities and deeper collaboration throughout the course of the project implementation.

Link: <https://pro-climate.eu/pro-climate-and-regions4climate/>

d. FARCLIMATE

PRO-CLIMATE has initiated a productive collaboration with the FAR-CLIMATE project, focusing on shared interests in climate resilience and stakeholder engagement. As part of this synergy, the two projects have jointly submitted a session proposal and will co-organize an interactive workshop at the upcoming Open Living Lab Days 2025 (OLLD25). The session will engage participants in hands-on exercises and discussions around the design and implementation of climate adaptation Living Labs, building on real-life project experiences. This collaboration marks an important step toward strengthening inter-project learning and cross-fertilization of methodologies.

4.3 Events

4.3.1 MIP4ADAPT - Thematic Working Groups

PRO-CLIMATE has been actively involved in the Mission Adaptation Community of Practice, participating in several Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) coordinated under the European Commission's Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. These TWGs serve as collaborative platforms to exchange knowledge, align methodologies, and co-create policy-relevant outputs among EU-funded projects and regional actors. Specifically, PRO-CLIMATE contributes to four key working groups: (a) Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement, (b) Climate Services, (c) Monitoring and

Evaluation, and (d) Transformational Adaptation. Through these groups, the project shares insights from its Living Lab experiences, methodological approaches for behavioral change, and governance innovation.

Engagement in these TWGs has allowed PRO-CLIMATE to both contribute to and benefit from a growing ecosystem of expertise. Project partners have participated in regular meetings and workshops, actively contributing to the co-development of policy briefs and guidance documents aimed at supporting regions and communities in their climate adaptation efforts. Moreover, the project is exploring opportunities to organize joint events and collaborative sessions with other Mission-affiliated projects, ensuring that collective knowledge is mobilized for greater policy and societal impact. This collaborative spirit not only reinforces the relevance of PRO-CLIMATE’s work but also aligns with the Mission’s overarching goals of accelerating transformative and inclusive adaptation pathways across Europe.

4.3.2 Innovation and Practice Groups

PRO-CLIMATE has actively participated in the first three Innovation and Practice Groups (IPGs) hosted by the Pathways2Resilience (P2R) project, focusing on the theme of Behavioral Change and Empowerment. These sessions provided a valuable forum for knowledge exchange and practical dialogue among European regions and projects engaged in climate adaptation. Through these IPGs, PRO-CLIMATE has shared insights from its Living Lab activities and discussed strategies for enabling social transformation. Notably, Prof. Ann-Marie Nienaber of Coventry University presented the project’s methodological approach to behavioral change, showcasing how PRO-CLIMATE integrates psychological and social science perspectives into systemic adaptation processes, during the 2nd IPG. This participation has reinforced the project’s visibility within the Mission community and has contributed to shaping shared practices across European adaptation initiatives.

4.3.3 Participation in other events

EURESFO

PRO-CLIMATE participated in the European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) 2025, a flagship event for advancing resilience in cities and regions across Europe. The project was represented by Prof. Ann-Marie Nienaber, who contributed to the session titled “Bridging Knowledge and Practice: A Deep Dive into Regional Climate Resilience” [link](#). This session explored how knowledge and tools developed through research can be effectively transferred into regional adaptation practices. Prof. Nienaber presented PRO-CLIMATE’s methodological insights on behavioral change and community empowerment, highlighting the project’s Living Lab experience and the role of social dynamics in fostering regional climate resilience. This high-profile participation underscores the project’s commitment to translating research into action and aligning with the broader European adaptation agenda.

Figure 18: PRO-CLIMATE's participation in EURESFO 2025

OLLD25

Tero, as coordinator of the PRO-CLIMATE project, will participate in the upcoming Open Living Lab Days 2025 (OLLD25) through a joint session proposal co-developed with the FAR-CLIMATE project. The session, titled “*From PRO to FAR: Co-Creating Climate Adaptation Living Labs*”, will take the form of an interactive workshop designed to immerse participants in hands-on activities, peer learning, and collaborative design. Drawing from real-life experiences of both projects, the workshop will guide attendees through scenario-based group exercises, with a focus on governance structures, behavioral change strategies, and stakeholder engagement practices in climate resilience. This collaborative initiative reflects PRO-CLIMATE’s commitment to cross-project learning and methodology sharing, and reinforces the project’s presence in key European innovation forums as also presented in Appendix 1.

4.4 Interviews

As part of the project’s dissemination and outreach efforts, an interview titled “*Community Empowerment for Climate Change Action*” was published on the AlterClimACT platform, highlighting the objectives and approach of PRO-CLIMATE. The interview emphasized the importance of engaging local communities and stakeholders in climate adaptation processes and showcased how the project aims to catalyze social and behavioral change for climate resilience. This communication activity contributed to raising awareness about the project’s mission and promoting its visibility among wider European and international audiences. The full interview is accessible online at:

<https://alterclimatechange.com/publication/pro-climate-interview-community-empowerment-climate-change-action>

Europe is already experiencing the effects of climate change.

*In 2024, the continent sweated through its **hottest year on record**, experiencing elevated heat stress and extreme weather events like fires and droughts.*

That means building resilient, climate-ready communities is no longer a distant goal—it’s an urgent necessity.

*Enter the **PRO-CLIMATE** project, an ambitious EU-funded initiative dedicated to transforming how communities adapt to and tackle climate change. By establishing six diverse “Living Labs” across Europe, PRO-*

Figure 19: PRO-CLIMATE’s PC Interview to Alter!

4.5 Upcoming sessions

In the upcoming months, the PRO-CLIMATE consortium will continue its proactive dissemination strategy through a series of joint activities designed to maximize visibility, foster knowledge exchange, and strengthen inter-project collaboration. A key event will be the joint workshop “From PRO to FAR”, co-organized with the FAR-CLIMATE project during the Open Living Lab Days 2025. This 90-minute session will follow an interactive format, engaging participants in group exercises to identify essential elements for climate resilience Living Labs based on real-life project scenarios. The workshop will guide participants through brainstorming sessions, stakeholder engagement strategies, and practical exercises for designing their own Living Lab concepts. Peer learning will be

promoted through group presentations and a concluding discussion, supported by the sharing of templates, tools, and next steps.

In parallel, PRO-CLIMATE is also preparing a joint webinar with the NEUROCLIMA project, which is currently under development. The webinar will focus on lessons learned and tools developed across both initiatives, while exploring key synergy points in the areas of behavioral change, community empowerment, and climate adaptation methodologies.

5 Conclusions

This interim Dissemination and Communication Impact Report (D7.3) reflects the efforts and achievements of the PRO-CLIMATE consortium during the first 18 months of the project in engaging stakeholders, raising awareness, and fostering collaboration. Through a well-coordinated strategy and the active involvement of all partners, the project has made significant progress in building its identity, ensuring visibility across Europe, and initiating meaningful dialogues with a wide spectrum of audiences—from citizens and policy makers to researchers and practitioners.

The results presented demonstrate not only the reach and diversity of the dissemination tools and channels used, but also the growing momentum of the project within the European climate adaptation landscape. The use of visual identity materials, the development and maintenance of a dynamic website and social media presence, the release of publications and newsletters, and the organisation and participation in high-profile events have contributed to the project's credibility and recognition.

Importantly, the project has taken concrete steps to build long-term partnerships with other EU-funded initiatives such as NEUROCLIMA, FAR-CLIMATE, Pathways2Resilience, and Regions4Climate. These collaborations enhance PRO-CLIMATE's impact potential and are already resulting in co-organised sessions, shared outputs, and a roadmap for joint dissemination in the second half of the project.

As the project moves forward, the insights and feedback gathered through D&C activities will inform adjustments to the strategy, ensuring continued alignment with project goals and stakeholder expectations. The final reporting in D7.4 will build upon this interim assessment to present a comprehensive view of how dissemination and communication have contributed to the project's broader mission: enabling proactive, community-based adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change.

Appendices

Appendix 1

Table 2: Dissemination Activities

No.	Title	Date	Type	Groups involved	Short description
1	Established communication between sister projects PRO-CLIMATE & NEUROCLIMA	January 2024	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities, Industry, business partners	
2	Participation in MIP4ADAPT	January 2024	Clustering activities	EU Institutions, Research communities, Industry, business partners	PRO-CLIMATE joined the Mission Implementation Platform and will collaborate with other EU projects.
3	"Communities for Climate Change Adaptation"	April 2024	Conferences	Innovators, EU Institutions, Research Communities	UG presented on the Scientific Conference at the University of Warsaw, the Gdansk LL
4	Participation in the 3rd International Conference 'Lakes & Reservoirs: Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology'	September 2024	Conference	Research Communities, Industry, Business partners	UG presented the results of the research on the Scientific Conference organized by the Polish Limnological Society and the University of Gdansk
5	IPG on Behavioural Change, P2R 1st session	November 2024	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	EU Institutions, Research communities	Tero participated representing PRO-CLIMATE
6	ATU participation in event	September 2024	Citizens, NGOs, Researchers	Physical event	ATU participated in the Remembering the Armada festival where the project was presented as well as the local LL. More than 200 people participated
7	PRO-CLIMATE at BMBF virtual workshop on integrating the gender dimension in research on climate (change)	December 2024	Education and training events	EU Institutions, Research communities, Industry, Business partners, National authorities, Regional authorities	CU and ULEI participated in a virtual workshop on integrating the gender dimensions in research on climate change organised by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research and German Aerospace Center (DLR)
8	IPG on Behavioural Change, P2R 2nd session	March 2025	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	EU Institutions, Research communities	CU through Prof. Ann-Marie Nienaber participated as an expert and presented the behavioural change process of PRO-CLIMATE

D7.3 Dissemination & Communication Impact Report Interim version

9	PRO-CLIMATE at GESIS	March 2025	Education and training events	EU Institutions, Research communities, Business partners	Alexander Yendell (ULEI) & Ann-Marie Nienaber (CU) presented the PRO-CLIMATE project at GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
10	17th Air and Water Components of the environment	March 2025	Conferences	Innovators, EU Institutions, Research Communities, Industry-business partners	UG presented the results of PRO-CLIMATE project at the University of Babeş-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca in Romania
11	PRO-CLIMATE at 11th ERIAFF CONFERENCE 2025	April 2025	Conferences	ERIAFF network members. EU Institutions, Research communities, Industry, Business partners, National authorities, Regional authorities, Local Authorities.	Pilar Muñoz Romero (DB) presented the PRO-CLIMATE project at 11th ERIAFF CONFERENCE 2025. Working group session on Missions. https://www.congresbit.cat/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/eriaff2025-wg-sessions-programme-v04-1.pdf
12	MPI4ADAPT Thematic Working Groups meetings and events	May 2025	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	EU Institutions, Research communities, Business partners, National authorities, Regional authorities	Tero is participating as the PC in all events and meeting as set and organised by the various Thematic Working Groups of MIP4ADAPT and collaborating with various EU projects.
13	EUROACE Demographic Challenge Committee.	March 2025	Regional authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Dissemination of the project in the first meeting of EUROACE (Cross-border region Extremadura (ES) Alentejo (PT) and Centro (PT)) Demographic Challenge Committee. More than 10 entities from Spain and Portugal received information about the project
14	2 nd Geogame symposium in Dublin	June 2025	Symposium	EU Institutions, Research communities, Business partners, National authorities, Regional authorities	Presented paper on "The use of serious games in Living Labs"
15	EURESFO	June 2025	Forum	EU Institutions, Research communities, Business partners, National authorities,	Prof. Ann-Marie Nienaber was invited as an expert speaker in a dedicated session on behavioural change

				Regional authorities	
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Appendix 2

Table 3: Communication activities

No.	Title	Description	Target groups	Type	Reach
1	Website release	The release of the 1st version of the PRO-CLIMATE website	Citizens	Website	More than 100 unique visitors
2	1st Press Release	Publication and communication of the project's 1st press release.	Citizens	Website	More than 200 people reached
3	Greek Article in Greenagenda.gr	Publication of an article about PRO-CLIMATE in a climate and green energy greek media website named www.greenagenda.gr (https://greenagenda.gr/pro-climate-%ce%b4%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b9%ce%bf%cf%85%cf%81%ce%b3%ce%af%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%bf%ce%bd%cf%84%ce%ad%ce%bb%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b3%ce%b9%ce%b1-%cf%84%ce%b7-%cf%87%ce%ac%cf%81%ce%b1%ce%be%ce%b7-%cf%80/)	Citizens	Media article	Audience to GreenAgenda more than 2000 visitors monthly
4	Project General Press Release	Published through WIT News (World of Innovation and Technology)	Citizens	Press release	More than 100 followers while additionally from reposts and LinkedIn algorithm promotion
5	Coventry University website	Information about PRO-CLIMATE project is presented to the website of CU: https://www.coventry.ac.uk/research/research-directories/projects/2024/adaptation-to-climate-change/	Citizens	Website	More than 500 researchers and citizens are expected to view the post
6	Badajoz website	https://desarrollorural.dip-badajoz.es/proyecto/pro-climate	Citizens	Website	More than 200 unique visitors

7	Badajoz press release	https://desarrollorural.dip-badajoz.es/entrada/noticias/pro-climate	Citizens	Website	More than 500 citizens reached
8	Badajoz press release	https://www.dip-badajoz.es/agenda/index.php?id=3&agenda=22421	Citizens	Website	More than 500 citizens reached
9	Badajoz visibility plaque	PRO-CLIMATE external plaque in the building of Rural Development, Demographic Challenge & Tourism Area	Citizens	Other	More than 500 citizens are expected to view it
10	Badajoz press release on 3rd GA	https://desarrollorural.dip-badajoz.es/entrada/noticias/badajoz-hacogido-la-tercera-asamblea-de-socios-del-proyecto-pro-climate	Citizens	Website	More than 500 citizens are expected to view it
11	Badajoz Press release	Press release on the workshop that took place in relation to the Pilot Operational Plans as part of WP2 and the 1 st Living Lab workshop with stakeholders (https://www.dip-badajoz.es/agenda/index.php?id=3&agenda=22734)	Citizens	Press release	More than 500 citizens are expected to view it
12	Badajoz Press release	Press release about PRO-CLIMATE project at 11th ERIAFF CONFERENCE 2025. Working group session on Missions. https://desarrollorural.dip-badajoz.es/entrada/noticias/xi-conferencia-anual-de-eriaff-2025-en-vic-cataluna	Citizens	Press release	More than 500 citizens are expected to view it
13	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 1st Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's website)	Citizens	Website	More than 250
14	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 1st Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's Facebook and LinkedIn accounts)	Citizens	Social media	More than 250
15	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 2nd Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's website)	Citizens	Website	More than 250
16	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 2nd Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's Facebook and LinkedIn accounts)	Citizens	Social media	More than 250
17	PRO-CLIMATE, 3rd General	Press release on the 3rd Consortium meeting in Badajoz (4-5 of February 2025)	Citizens	Website	More than 350

	Assembly Meeting 4-5 February 2025				
18	PRO-CLIMATE, 3rd General Assembly Meeting 4-5 February 2025	Press release on the 3rd Consortium meeting in Badajoz (4-5 of February 2025)	Citizens	Social media	More than 750
19	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 3rd Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's website)	Citizens	Website	More than 250
20	Living Lab Zakynthos Press release	Press release about the 3rd Living Lab meeting in Zakynthos (press release posted on Co-opAbility's Facebook and LinkedIn accounts)	Citizens	Social media	More than 250
21	Social media posts	Constant social media posts across all social media channels	General public	Social media	More than 5000 views overall
22	Faculty of Oceanography and Geography UG website	Information about PRO-CLIMATE project is presented to the website of UG: https://oig.ug.edu.pl/news/111199/projekt-pro-climate-w-katedrze-hydrologii	Citizens	Website	More than 100
23	Library of Univeristy of Gdansk	Press release about the PRO-CLIMATE project: https://www.repozytorium.bg.ug.edu.pl/info/projectmain/UOG694e0bb76862444cb5f23af07d22a0eb?r=projectmain&ps=20&tab=main&title=Projekty%2B%25E2%2580%2593%2BProaktywna%2Bbadajacz%2Bsp%25C5%2582eczno%25C5%259Bci%2Bdo%2Bzmian%2Bklimatu%2Bpoprzez%2Btransformacj%25C4%2599%2Bsp%25C5%2582eczn%25C4%2585%2Bi%2Bzmian%25C4%2599%2Bzachowa%25C5%2584%2B%25E2%2580%2593%2BUniwersytet%2BGda%25C5%2584ski&lang=pl&pn=1	Citizens	Website	More than 150
24	Polish Science website	Press release about PRO-CLIMATE project: https://polishscience.pl/pl/universytet-gdanski-otrzymal-dofinansowanie-na-projekt-pro-climate/	Research communities	Website	More than 120

25	University of Gdansk website	Press release about PRO-CLIMATE project: https://ug.edu.pl/news/pl/5541/universytet-gdanski-uczestniczy-wspolpracy-miedzynarodowej-w-projekcie-dotyczacym-zmian-klimatu	Citizens	Website	More than 500
26	Offshore Wind Poland website	Press release about PRO-CLIMATE project: https://offshorewindpoland.pl/tag/pro-climate/	Investors	Website	More than 100
27	Gdansk LL Press Release on Gdansk Co-creation Workshop	Press release about Co-creation Workshop in Gdansk: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/pro-climate-project_first-steps-toward-establishing-the-gda%C5%84sk-activity-7327660372402831360-Bgu2/	Citizens	Social media	More than 1000
28	Gdansk LL Press Release on Scientists in Schools PRO-CLIMATE workshops in Hevelianum Science Centre in Gdańsk	https://www.facebook.com/hevelianum/posts/pfbid02dQhh85dJcH9csvPbHcbq2WZvjxoEW196xQ62SPpYLJ6BjmWBMLDJynwcCQ81TqpLI	Citizens	Social media	More than 250
29	Gdansk LL Press Release on Scientists in Schools PRO-CLIMATE workshops in Hevelianum Science Centre in Gdańsk	Press release about Scientist in Schools in Hevelianum: https://hevelianum.pl/wydarzenia/naukowcy-w-szkolach-wyklady-i-warsztaty-dla-szkol-9-06-2025/	Citizens	Press release	More than 130
30	Gdansk LL Press Release on Scientists in Schools PRO-CLIMATE	Newsletter/invitation for Scientists in Schools: https://hevelianum.pl/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Naukowcy-w-szkolach-2025-Hevelianum-2.pdf	Citizens	Newsletter	More than 50

	workshops in Hevelianum Science Centre in Gdańsk				
31	Gdansk LL Press Release on Scientists in Schools PRO-CLIMATE workshops in Hevelianum Science Centre in Gdańsk	Press release - invitation for workshops and lectures - Scientists in Schools: https://hevelianum.pl/naukowcy-w-szkolach-wyklady-i-warsztaty-dla-szkol/	Citizens	Press release	More than 500
32	Hevelianum Instagram	Recap of Scientists in Schools: https://www.instagram.com/p/DLMhGe9sNWo/?img_index=1	Citizens	Social media	